

Main Directions of Sociolinguistics

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Abstract. *This article discusses the main directions of sociolinguistics and their tasks. Synchronous and diachronic, macro and micro sociolinguistics, theoretical and practical sociolinguistics are discussed separately, and a broader understanding of their study objects is given.*

Key words: *language, language development, objects of sociolinguistics, synchronic sociolinguistics, diachronic sociolinguistics, macro sociolinguistics, micro sociolinguistics, theoretical sociolinguistics, applied sociolinguistics.*

One of the main areas of sociolinguistics is synchronic and diachronic linguistics. These aspects of the study of language in linguistics have been distinguished since the time of Ferdinand de Saussure. Language such a division in learning also exists in sociolinguistics. "Synchronous sociolinguistics language and studies relations and processes related to social relations. Relationships are relationships statistics, and processes represent their dynamics".

Synchronous sociolinguistics considered the relationship between language and society and studies processes. Relationships are the statics of relationships, and processes represents their dynamics. The owner of one or another language has certain social characteristics, in particular, a certain education degree, profession, system of value orientation, etc. "Language Owner" and the reciprocal relationship of the status of "owner of social characteristics" has passed in time is not related to any processes. But different social nature the study of language use characteristics of people who have it, outside of these conditions, only by observing the process of speech communication can be achieved. Statics are replaced by dynamics.

In a multilingual society, languages are edited according to the ethnicity of the speakers distributed: for example, in today's Russia, together with Russians, Tatars, Yakuts, Ossetians and other peoples also live there, each of them has their own native language. At this point, it should be noted that the relationship between languages and ethnic groups is the same it will not happen: on the one hand, many nations do not know their mother tongue accounts from other languages widely used in society; another on the other hand, there are languages such as Swahili, "the native speakers of this language there is no ethnic group, because in Africa it is an autochthonous ethnos whose mother tongue is Swahili not available".

Synchronous sociolinguistics is an example for us to see the characteristic aspect of language in different periods let's say: "Let's say, the old Uzbek literary language of the 6th century, the Uzbek language of the 7th-19th centuries and the 20th century the Uzbek literary language at the beginning and the laws of its development from a synchronous (modern) point of view can be learned from the point of view".

The main task of synchronic sociolinguistics is whatever language it is in the world is to study its current appearance, the life of ethnic groups and countries. In a word, synchronic sociolinguistics, social aspects of language, literary language, colloquial language, dialects. Linguistic socialization,

language acquisition in the field of synchronous sociolinguistics mastering the system of social roles, knowing the basics of "situational grammar" and includes learning in relation to others. Synchronous sociolinguistics L. Nikolsky, J. Fishman, J. Gumpers, and D. Hyams on the field of practice in more detail in "Directions in Sociolinguistics" (1972), ed information is provided.

Diachronic sociolinguistics The Greek word "diachron" means "related to two periods". means Diachronic sociolinguistics is different from synchronic sociolinguistics. Diachron sociolinguistics studies the historical development of the language, the movement system. Basically, speak up covering the stages of the language that has been formed until now takes In sociolinguistics, the development task of the language is mainly related to the variability of the language. Diachronic sociolinguistics can solve many problems. Language historical formation of development, socio-historical types, laws of language, social meaning .Several issues such as expression are the task of diachronic sociolinguistics.

Diachronic sociolinguistics is the social development of language development connecting the processes that show the connection, that is, the history of the language with the history of the people is a branch of sociolinguistic research. Systematic, gradual interaction of language facts and social processes Determining the relationship is characteristic of sociolinguistic research. If a researcher in the process of studying the history of a language, events related to the history of the people if he just noted it, then such a work as a sociolinguistic study it will be difficult to accept. If the research is internal, characteristic of language development the impact of laws and external social factors on language development is clear if it is based on demarcation and the impact of language changes on this or that phenomenon if analyzed, then such work is called a diachronic sociolinguistic study can be said.

According to the scale of the objects of sociolinguistics, **macro** and is divided into **micro** sociolinguistics. Macro and micro sociolinguistics differentiation of sociology into macro- and micro-sociology in a certain sense it looks like a divorce. Therefore, macro sociology of the whole society with global processes related to its development and operation If engaged in micro sociology, a person is a member of one or another social group is interesting. Some authors consider language phenomena in macro and micro directions distinguished as layers of sociolinguistic analysis (e.g., Berruto 1974, Chapter 4). However, throughout the development of sociolinguistics, these levels of analysis became independent and sociolinguistics are two less intersecting turned into a direction.

Macro sociolinguistics with social factors at one level or another studies conditioned large-scale processes. It is a process and a relationship to society as a whole or to its large complex: social stratum, ethnos, ethnicity. It is characteristic of the group. For example, the social differentiation of language learning includes the macro level: this national language and its sub-systems takes. A macro approach is prevalent in many studies of bilingualism observed; language standardization and codification problems, as well as Language policy and language planning issues are primarily macro is studied within the sociolinguistic approach.

Micro sociolinguistics, as its name says, organizes the use of language in small groups: family, school, enterprise, organizations. Language tools used in small communities are not considered, but they have more tools related to language development. A small team to eliminate some of the language problems in the society by listening to their words possible Because a person is basically embodied in the image of a "creator". In Micro Sociolinguistics speech dialogues of team members mother-in-law and daughter-in-law, father and mother, teacher and students research is extensive.

In short, the directions of sociolinguistics are synchronic and diachronic sociolinguistics, macro and micro sociolinguistics, applied and theoretical sociolinguistics all are aimed at fulfilling the main task of the language and contributing to the development of the language. The field of sociolinguistics studies the relationship between society and language, while sociolinguistics directions will provide an opportunity to study these relationships more deeply.

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